

septic shock, and longitudinally, on admission (0 hours), and 4, 12, 24, 48, 120 and 240 hours thereafter, eight polytraumatized patients were monitored. ISS, SAPS3 and SOFA score reflect severity of injury, of disease and of organ dysfunctions.

Results In polytraumatized patients (24 hours measurement), but also in septic patients, CD88⁺ expression and CD33⁺/CD66b⁻ expression were significantly lower and CD33⁻/CD66b⁺ higher than in healthy controls. Especially, the lowest values of CD88⁺ occurred in patients with polytrauma developing septic complications.

Furthermore, the polytraumatized patients revealed higher levels of CD66b, CD11b and CD16, whereas CD16⁺ was lower. Considering the post-traumatic course, polytraumatized patients with better prognostic evaluation in SOFA and SAPS3 initially expressed higher levels of TLR-2. Polytrauma patients could be divided into two subgroups, one with and the other without septic complications. The septic subgroup presented predominantly higher values in SOFA, SAPS3 and ISS scoring.

Conclusion Cell surface molecules on PMN of polytraumatized patients differ from those of healthy volunteers. Besides, distinct expression patterns resemble those of patients with sepsis. Patients with higher ISS values go along with higher scores in SOFA and SAPS3, and are at risk to develop septic complications.

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Lymphocyte surface expression patterns differ in inflammatory and infectious stages in polytraumatized and septic shock patients

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Introduction Lymphocytes show different cell surface molecules depending on the degree of their activation or suppression. We used this surface expression to look at inflammatory or infectious states in patients with polytrauma and patients with sepsis. The present study was performed to clarify: what is the expression profile of lymphocyte surface markers in polytraumatized patients over time; and are there differences in the expression patterns of polytraumatized patients compared with healthy controls and with patients with severe sepsis and septic shock?

Methods In a prospective observational study in a surgical ICU, surface expression of CD3, CD4, CD8, IL7R, CD4/25, CD8/25, CD2/86, CD28, CD3/56, CD2, CD39, CD244, CD11b, and CD56 on lymphocytes was measured by flow cytometry. We collected data from six healthy controls, from eight patients with severe sepsis or septic shock, and longitudinally from eight polytraumatized patients on admission (0 hours), and at 4, 12, 24, 48, 120, and 240 hours. ISS, SAPS 3 and SOFA score reflect severity of injury, of disease and of organ dysfunctions of the polytraumatized patients.

Results In septic and polytraumatized patients, the expression of CD3, CD28 and CD2 was significantly lower than in controls. In polytraumatized patients, surface expression of CD244, CD39 and CD8/25 was significantly higher than in controls. Within the polytraumatized patients, we found two different subgroups, group A with septic progression and Group B without septic progression of disease. Especially, the septic polytraumatized patients revealed very low levels of CD3, CD2 and CD28. Moreover, their levels of CD39 and CD8/25 were less increased and their ISS higher than those of the nonseptic subgroup.

Conclusion Surface expression molecules of polytraumatized patients differ from those of the healthy controls and within the group. The more heavily injured polytraumatized patients are more likely to develop severe sepsis and septic shock with surface expression profiles on lymphocytes comparable with those of septic patients.

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Cl:Na ratio on ICU admission as a prognostic indicator of mortality in sepsis patients

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Introduction The aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between Cl:Na ratio disturbances and mortality in sepsis patients.

Figure 1 (abstract P230). In the multivariate model, effect of Cl:Na ratio group was adjusted for pH, lactate, anion gap and base excess.

Stewart's strong ion theory can be used in the interpretations of acid-base abnormalities [1]. The Cl:Na ratio is a simple alternative test that obviates the need to solve the complex strong ion gap (SIG) equations [2].

Methods A total of 434 sepsis and severe sepsis patients hospitalized in the ICU of two centers between 2006 and 2012 were included in the study. Three groups were formed as patients having low (<0.75), normal (>0.75 to <0.80) and high (>0.80) Cl:Na ratio within the first 24 hours in the ICU. Patients' age, gender, APACHE II score, SOFA score, pH, PaCO₂, HCO₃⁻, base excess, Na, K, Cl, Ca, lactate, strong ion difference, anion gap, length of ICU stay and mortality were recorded. Logistic regression analysis was used to calculate odd ratios and 95% CIs for the association of Cl:Na with mortality. In the fully adjusted model, pH, BE, AG, lactate and Cl:Na ratio were entered into the model. *P* < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results The distribution of the patients was as follows: low Cl:Na (75, 17%), normal Cl:Na (243, 56%), high Cl:Na (116, 27%). Univariate analysis revealed that in low and high Cl:Na ratio patients, mortality was higher by 1.56-fold (0.87 to 2.81) and 2.22-fold (1.36 to 3.61) (*P* = 0.135 and *P* < 0.01). In multivariate analysis, increased mortality by 1.95-fold (0.92 to 4.12) and 2.02-fold (1.01 to 4.03) was found in low and high Cl:Na ratios (*P* = 0.081 and *P* = 0.046) (Figure 1).

Conclusion Stewart's strong ion theory provides assessment for the etiology of acid-base disturbances. This evaluation can be performed easier and faster with the Cl:Na ratio. This study demonstrates that the disturbed Cl:Na ratio is associated with increased mortality in sepsis and severe sepsis patient groups.

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Dysfunction of peroxisomes as one of the possible causes of multiple organ dysfunction syndrome development

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Introduction This study demonstrates that low level of plasmalogens (PIs) is an important marker of peroxisomal dysfunction. The primary-OH group in glycerol PIs was not substituted by the acyl group (fatty acid) as in diacylphospholipids but by the aldehydogenic alkenyl group (fatty aldehyde) found in the form of vinyl ether [1]. It is known that there is disruption of several organ systems in diseases connected with peroxisomal dysfunction, as in the case of multiple organ failure.

Methods The objects of study were 18 people with multiple organ failure (35.6 ± 8.7 years) of various etiologies. The blood of 16 healthy

volunteers aged 37.7 ± 3.2 years served as control. The preanalytical phase was to prepare a solution of ethyl esters of fatty acids (FAc) and diethylacetals of fatty aldehydes (FAI) of blood plasma samples by acidic ethanolsis. Analysis of FAI and FAc in plasma was carried out using capillary gas-liquid chromatography. Quantitative evaluation of the analytes was performed as a mass percentage of the FA and FAI amount. Statistical analysis was performed using the Mann-Whitney U test ($P < 0.05$).

Results In contradistinction to triglycerides, diacylphospholipids and Pls participate in exchange of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) with a large number of double bonds, such as primarily arachidonic and docosahexaenoic PUFA, acting as an intermediate station, through which these fatty acids are transported to cell membranes [1]. Thus, the ratio of level of FAI to the level of aforementioned blood plasma PUFA may reflect a change in the share of Pls relative to diacylphospholipids. According to our data, at MODS the ratio of fatty aldehydes to amount of arachidonic and docosahexaenoic PUFA is 0.16, while in the control group the figure is 0.27 ($P < 0.001$). Thus, we can conclude that the level of Pls towards diacylphospholipid plasma levels of the experimental group decreased by approximately 40%. Currently, there is evidence that there is a reduction of cholesterol levels in blood plasma of patients with the diseases associated with peroxisome biogenesis disorders [2]. In our study, patients had low levels of plasma total cholesterol (124.6 ± 28.7 mg/dl), which may also indicate peroxisome dysfunction in MODS patients.

Conclusion On the basis of determined deficiency of analyzed compound levels, we concluded the possibility of peroxysomal dysfunction in MODS.

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Differential effect of alcohol on TNF α receptor II production in the presence of LPS challenge *ex vivo*

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Introduction Acute alcohol exposure suppresses proinflammatory response, which may be related to increased susceptibility to infections [1]. The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of acute exposure to alcohol on TNF α production capacity and TNF α receptors (TNFRs) in an *ex vivo* model of whole-blood stimulation with lipopolysaccharide (LPS).

Methods Whole blood was taken from healthy volunteers and was placed in tubes containing EDTA and immediately transferred to the laboratory. Heparinized blood samples were diluted 1:10 in RPMI 1640 culture medium (100 μ l whole blood added in 900 μ l RPMI 1640). Samples were preincubated with 0, 5, 12.5, 25, 50, 100 and 200 mM alcohol (EtOH) for 10 minutes at room temperature. After incubation, 500 pg LPS was added to each sample for 4 hours at 37°C. At the end of the process, samples were centrifuged (1,800 rpm, 5 minutes, r.t.). Culture supernatants were collected and stored at -70°C until measurements. TNF α and TNFR levels were determined in culture supernatant using the ELISA method [2].

Results We studied 24 healthy males volunteers aged 36.5 ± 1.4 ($X \pm SEM$). TNF α was not detected in samples treated without alcohol in the absence of LPS stimulation (control) or in the presence of alcohol alone (data not shown). TNF α production was significantly decreased at a dose of 25 mM alcohol after LPS stimulation ($P < 0.0001$) compared with LPS-challenged samples (Figure 1A). Alcohol had no effect on TNFR I production when incubated with or without LPS (data not shown). Alcohol at lower doses (<50 mM) seemed to decrease TNFR II levels, but an increase in TNFR II levels was observed at higher doses (>50 mM) of alcohol, which was statistically significant at doses of 100 and 200 mM alcohol after LPS stimulation *ex vivo* ($P < 0.001$) (Figure 1B).

Conclusion Our observations indicate a suppression of proinflammatory response, but also a differential effect of alcohol on TNFR II production of whole blood in the presence of LPS challenge depending on the degree of alcohol intoxication.

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Neutrophil phenotype model for extracorporeal treatment of sepsis

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Introduction Neutrophils play a central role in eliminating bacterial pathogens, but may also contribute to end-organ damage. Interleukin-8 (IL-8), a key modulator of neutrophil function, signals through neutrophil specific surface receptors CXCR-1 and CXCR-2. Expression of these surface receptors can be altered by perfusion through an extracorporeal device. Extracorporeal methods of immune modulation have shown promise for treatment of sepsis; however, achieving an appropriate response is a major challenge [1]. In this study a mechanistic mathematical model was used to evaluate and deploy an extracorporeal sepsis treatment that modulates CXCR-1/2 levels.

